

SOCIOLOGICAL GAZE OF TARE ZAMEEN PAR

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Abstract

Each and every film has different terrain of thoughts to see the ongoing structure of society. A film depends on the viewers how are they interpret or the ways of thinking based on the film in the essence of the society. A civil encoder tries to send messages throughout the film and then leaves it to the audience for decoding. Sociology is a subject where the subject itself helps us to build the parameters and gaze to know the society and understand the society better. In this paper researcher has chosen the film called “Tare Zameen Par” as content to analysis better in sociological terrain. In this paper researcher has tried to denote how the parents treat a child when he/she is suffering from unknown disorder which wasn’t introduced beforehand. And it presented how it should be treated how should be the socialization process. People are completely blind in between marks and ideal types, an unspoken and invisible rat race we all are involuntarily participated, this are all have discussed in further.

Key Words: Socialization, Medical disorder, Ideal type, Taboo.

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Introduction:

As we all known and have watched the famous Hindi film called “Tare Zameen Par”, how does the film showed that it can be explained in various ways but majorly it can be elaborated or understood through the sociological approach. Firstly in the whole film a child played a leading role and his name was Ishan Nandkisor Avasti. From the researcher’s point of view the film Tare Zameen Par tried to explain how the individual became important to us, how should he be treated to that individual, as we all have seen the Ishan was suffering from Dyslexia and how the main socialization agent called family treated him and that individual then how Aamir Khan as a teacher came as the main game changer which means when someone is deviated from the mainstream society then how to be treated and returned back the individual to the main stream society, because as per the post modernists thought that narrow narratives rather than grand narratives is important, as per as Thomas Kuhn and his book of “The Structure of Scientific Revolution” where he discussed about the “Paradigm Shift” which he tried to understand a crisis or an anomaly is important because each and every individual is important, in research when a sample puzzles the whole structure of research becomes muddle, that doesn’t mean to reject, if it happens then the crisis begins and the paradigm shift happens, then it changes the whole structure of paradigm, as

per as the film where the anomaly is the children among the society. While we sociologist studying the society not as a whole but as an individual in the micro perspective but in macro perspective it's different or I can say its opposite. In this film the chronic disorder calls Dyslexia was newly emerged or unknown to that of Ishan's parents simultaneously all the socialization agents like school, peer group in the beginning of the game stage. It means a learning disorder characterized by difficulty in reading. And as per as the film I realized that not only from dyslexia he was also suffering from Dysgraphia (when someone felling trouble in learning) and another disorder which could be added in this context was Dysnomia (when someone couldn't measure height; distance; direction and speed). The primary focus of this paper is to denote how the parents who are members of a society treat their children who are apparently different from the societal child and thus making mental health as a deviance or a taboo.

The key to medicalization consists, "a process whereby more and more of everyday life have come under medical dominion, influence and supervision". P. Conrad sees it as, "defining behavior as a medical problem or illness and mandating the medical profession to provide some type of treatment for it". . What the film tried to explain.

Objectives:

Anyway the aim of this paper is directed understand the various aspect of this film, and these are

- i) How the film Tare Zameen Par interlinked with Medical Sociology.
- ii) Is it really a taboo when someone is suffering from dyslexia?
- iii) Does society have an Ideal Type? Is that we have to follow or what does it really mean?

Research approach and Method:

Methodological approaches to research in a Film calls "Tare Zameen Par" from the perspective of sociological context. The term includes varying degree of Content analysis. And the researcher took the qualitative method while doing this research.

Data Analysis:

In medical sociology the terrain of health and illness looked quite different and becoming so specialized in twenty first century. In the past thirty years medical professionals have identified several problems that have become commonly known illness and disorders. And such syndrome that relate to behavior, a psychic state, or bodily condition that now has a medical diagnosis and medical treatment. Now the medical treatment of medicines can able identify the illness which has way more developed and now the daily life's problem have received medical diagnoses and are subject to medical treatment. We can examine the medicalization of human problem and bracket the question of whether they are real medical problems. What constitutes a real medical problem may be largely in the eyes of the beholder or in the realm of those who have the authority to define a problem as medical. It is the viability of recognition rather than the viability of the diagnosis that is grist for the sociological mill. As per as the film "Tare Zameen Par" have shown itself. The boy couldn't even write properly, couldn't even measure a distance and couldn't even imagine whatever he have studied as compare to the other societal child but during his childhood no-one couldn't even recognized or else his father thinks that he is making silly mistakes knowingly, comparatively which mistakes a societal child never make knowingly or unknowingly. Without identifying his problem behind his action his parents leave him a boarding school. Does it call a process of socialization or else a part of it?

How much we are evolving or experiencing in day to day life us seeing that people are becoming more homogeneous to heterogeneous, universalistic to particularistic, diffuseness to specificity.

How much we are developing ourselves more we alienated. Whether in recognition or diagnostic the medical profession becomes way more broad or specialized. But here is the problem I found in this film that we are developing no doubt but the non-material culture far more under developed. In this sense cultural lag happens, because the society can't accept the anomaly because of his dyslexia syndrome while he is also a part of a society. Neither can we recognize not we diagnose. Like in Ishan's parents tried to get him in this mainstream society by hook or by crook that's why, what he is suffering it has become a taboo for his parents or society especially for his father. While his father has a burning example (Ishan's brother) to compare with. And still he was comparing himself with his elder brother, where there has no competition because both are different from their own way, like Ishan's painting and imagination is truly fantastic and expressive but they can't even bother about that. As per as Ishan's father there has no point to emphasize his that attribute as compared to the society partially it's true but parents who are the first agent of socialization and their recognition is more important than the society in the game stage.

According to this film or regarding the objectives in sociology we study classical thinker like Max Weber. According to Weber, he gave the theory calls Ideal type which means "as measuring rods or as means to find out similarities and differences in the actual phenomena. In fact, it is one of the methods of comparative study". Weber used as a concept as an abstract model, and when used as a standard of comparison. The abstract model of comparison in this film is Ishan's brother where Ishan never compete with him or else the whole society. But by force it has tried to inject by his father, why this kind of Ideal type? Where the top scorer always is on the top of the level and takes them as an example or an ideal type and compare others from their marks and point of view and every time it's lagging. And that leads to anxiety, depression and alienation as we have already seen that in this film.

Conclusion:

Medicalization occurs here as part of doctor-patient interaction, when a physician defines a problem as medical form of treatment. Thus it becomes clearer that medicalization is a broad definitional process, which may or may not directly include physicians and their treatments. As the film tried to explain to us that not each and everyone is same some of them are different, that doesn't mean that they are a taboo. But sometimes society treats as a taboo. As the film teaches us how should be treated while a child or a person mentally ill or differently able, They need more attention, more love, and care and identify them differently and try to understand themselves from their own understanding to evaluate and diagnose so that they also can be come into the mainstream society.

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